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SCALABILITY AND EDGE COMPUTING OPTIMIZATION

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Abstract	The deliverable D3.2 presents the IoT data sources added in the second half of the AD4GD project and the latest updates of the components used to handle the different IoT data encountered in the pilots. Furthermore, the deliverable addresses the topic of edge computing, in particular its scalability and optimization.
Keywords	IoT, integration, interoperability, APIs, edge computing, optimization, scalability
Disclaimer	Views and opinions expressed in this deliverable are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the United Kingdom, or Switzerland. Neither the European Union nor United Kingdom nor Switzerland can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CTMS	Camera Trap Metadata Standard
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol

HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCS	Low -Cost Sensor
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces Linked Data
NGSI-v2	Next Generation Service Interfaces version 2
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PaaS	Platform as a Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
SWE	Sensor Web Enablement
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D3.2 “Scalability and edge computing optimization” presents the updates of the heterogeneous IoT data sources encountered in the three pilots of the AD4GD project. The first pilot concerns the water quantity and quality in the lakes located in Berlin, Germany. The second pilot studies the biodiversity in the region of Catalonia. Finally, the third pilot is dedicated to the air quality. All the pilots are using IoT data and different components and building blocks were developed during the AD4GD project. The updates of these components are described in this deliverable. Furthermore, the SIMPL middleware initiative is also discussed in the deliverable D3.2. The edge computing is an important part of the Internet of Things in the context of the AD4GD project: this topic is presented in a dedicated chapter where different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to edge computing are specified. Finally, some actions to improve these KPIs are proposed, followed by several recommendations.

1 INTRODUCTION

The WP3 is responsible for the integration of heterogeneous IoT data into the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) designed in the AD4GD project. The main objectives of the activities done in the WP3 are the definition of the technical specification for the integration of heterogeneous IoT data, the tools required to implement this integration, in particular the multi-protocol proxy as a service which converts data from an input protocol or format to an output protocol or format in correspondence within the requirements specified in the first part of the AD4GD project. Different protocols and related formats are supported by the multi-protocol proxy as a service.

The edge computing is an important part for the IoT data integration and its optimization and scalability were studied during the AD4GD project. The results are reported in this deliverable. In particular, some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined to better evaluate the implementation done at the level of the edge computing.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The deliverable D3.2 reports the activities done in the context of the WP3 which is composed by three different tasks listed below:

- Task T3.1 “Heterogeneous IoT data integration model” (M1-M33)
- Task T3.2 “IoT multi-protocol parser as a service” (M1-M33)
- Task T3.3 “Scalability and edge computing optimization” (M13-M33)

A model for the integration of the heterogeneous IoT data has been defined in the Task T3.1, including the utilisation of open APIs. This model has taken into account the results provided by the other WPs.

The implementation of the multi-protocol parser as a service was done in the Task T3.2. Different communication and application protocols are available to handle the IoT data used by the three pilots of the AD4GD project.

Different KPIs concerning the scalability and the optimization of the edge computing are defined and presented in this deliverable in the context of the Task T3.3.

2 IOT DATA SOURCES

This chapter presents all the IoT data sources used by the three pilots of the AD4GD project. The first pilot is the water quantity and quality implemented in the city of Berlin in Germany. The second addresses the biodiversity in the region of Catalonia in Spain. Finally, the third pilot is the investigation on how the low-cost IoT sensors could contribute to the prediction of the air quality in Europe.

2.1 PILOT 1 (WATER QUANTITY AND QUALITY)

As previously mentioned in the deliverable D3.1 “Heterogeneous IoT data integration model”, it is important for the local authorities and other involved stakeholders to know the current state of the small lakes in the city of Berlin. The Internet of Things (IoT) allows the monitoring of the small lakes and the collection of data associated to the water quality and level. Different sources of IoT data are used in the pilot in Berlin and are listed below :

- Berlin Wasserportal (<https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php>): An API permits to retrieve CSV files for lakes in Berlin. There are two categories of CSV files depending on the types of measurements:
 - Water temperature: The data concerning the water temperature from 15 lakes are collected. The small lakes are namely Flughafensee, Plötzensee, Schäfersee, Malchower See, Oranksee, Obersee, Fennpfuhl, Biesdorfer Baggersee, Lietzensee, Halensee, Hundekehlesee, Grossglienicker See, Grunewaldsee, Dreipfuhl and Waldsee Zehlendorf.
 - Water level: In this case, the data containing the water level of 18 lakes are collected. These lakes are the same as above and the following three small lakes: Weisser See, Fennsee and Dianasee.
- AquaTroll 100 sensor: This dataset was provided as an example water sensor output at the beginning of the AD4GD project. This sensor provides a CSV file containing the water temperature, the specific conductivity and the total dissolved solids in the water.
- Oxygen sensor: This sensor was installed in a small lake and sends the data to an SFTP server. The data contain the concentration of oxygen in this lake and are stored under the form of a CSV file.
- Bright Sky (<https://brightsky.dev>): This online service provides an API which accesses the weather data in Berlin. The original measurements concerning the weather are made by the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD). This is an open-source project publishing the weather data using a simple JSON API.
- Open Meteo (<https://open-meteo.com/>): This free online service is also publishing the weather data around Berlin. It was selected to replace the Bright Sky to meet better the requirements of the pilot in Berlin. The data of the weather are available in two formats: JSON and CSV. Both file formats are used in the context of the AD4GD project.
- CrowdWater (<https://crowdwater.ch/en/start/>): This project initiated by the University of Zurich is based on Citizen Science. Indeed, a mobile application is available and the users can report on this application the different observations they have made by visiting the small lakes in Berlin. Typically, a user can enter the water level, the water colour, the number of people or animals in the water or near the water or further characteristics. The results are stored and published on CSV files. This mobile application is very useful to get manual observations concerning the water quality and level of the lakes located in Berlin.

2.2 PILOT 2 (BIODIVERSITY)

Pilot 2 deals with terrestrial habitat connectivity in Catalonia and the provision of integrated data to users, and in particular, to decision and policy makers. This pilot consists of time series Land Use Land Cover maps derived from satellite data every 5 years starting from 1987 to the present. From these maps, Terrestrial Habitat Connectivity is calculated for every pixel and also some ML techniques are applied for future scenarios. These analyses are species-agnostic, but some attempts to aggregate species information have been done via GBIF occurrences and IoT camera traps data.

Camera traps are used in this pilot to detect and identify the presence of given species. STA standard and FROST server are used to manage these observations.

Figure 1: General workflow for the acquisition of the camera trap observations

In this case, there are two kinds of Observations: "pictures" (taken by a camera trap) and "species", that are species occurrences identified by an expert in the pictures. Some attempts have been done to automatically identify species by using AI. In particular, PyrVisión¹ python package developed by CTFC and CVC has been tested. Further work needs to be done to fully incorporate this technology into the automatic workflow shown above.

Observations captured are part of two different Datastreams and each species occurrence is linked to respective pictures by an ObservationGroup. The FeatureOfInterest in both types of Observations, that is "Pictures" and "Species", are equal to the Location, due to the fact that the measurement was done in the same location as the Thing.

As already stated in D3.1, pictures not containing any animal or that contains persons are discarded and never transmitted to the cloud. However, further studies must be done to consider the usefulness of the non-animal presence images as one of the problems with species occurrences is the treatment of the NODATA vs the non-occurrence data and how to distinguish them. Moreover, these "empty" images, contain information on the time and the temperature so could also be considered as to provide other type of measurements. This new approach, though, will imply more images and observations to be sent and store to the FROST server and how this should be treated in terms of data streams and scalability.

¹ <https://github.com/ArnauCampanera/PyrVision>

In the current approach, “non-useful” images are discarded but the needed ones are neither uploaded into the FROST server. Pushing an image of the animal to the cloud was considered not to make sense in this use case and also for performance reasons: indeed, sending an image consumes some bandwidth; on the other hand, only some little bytes are required to transmit the time of the observation and the species name. Avoiding sending the pictures makes it also more compliant with GDPR as avoids the issue of sending an image which accidentally may contain a person.

Examples of some camera traps data streams:

- Occurrences:

[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(58\)/Datastreams\(35\)/Observations?\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\).FeatureOfInterest\(\\$select=feature\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?$expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)).FeatureOfInterest($select=feature))

```
@iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)"
@iot.id: 1393312
phenomenonTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
result: "https://www.gbif.org/species/7193910"
resultTime: "2024-07-20T09:00:00Z"
▼ Datastream:
  ▼ unitOfMeasurement:
    name: null
    symbol: null
    definition: null
  ▼ ObservedProperty:
    definition: "https://www.gbif.org/species"
  ▼ FeatureOfInterest:
    ▼ feature:
      type: "Point"
      ▼ coordinates:
        0: 2.942919
        1: 42.47697
DataStream@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)/Datastream"
FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)/FeatureOfInterest"
Objects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)/Objects"
ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)/ObservationGroups"
Subjects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)/Subjects"
```

- Pictures of a camera trap:

[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(59\)/Datastreams\(36\)/Observations?\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\).FeatureOfInterest\(\\$select=feature\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(59)/Datastreams(36)/Observations?$expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)).FeatureOfInterest($select=feature))


```

@iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)"
@iot.id: 1393314
phenomenonTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
result: "https://www.infoambiental.arumets.cat/AD4GD_CameraTrap/04072024_0612_C3/04072024_0612_C3_02.JPG"
resultTime: "2024-07-20T09:00:00Z"
▼ Datastream:
  ▼ unitOfMeasurement:
    name: null
    symbol: null
    definition: null
  ▼ ObservedProperty:
    definition: "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Image"
▼ FeatureOfInterest:
  ▼ feature:
    type: "Point"
    ▼ coordinates:
      0: 2.942919
      1: 42.47697
DataStream@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)/Datastream"
FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)/FeatureOfInterest"
Objects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)/Objects"
ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)/ObservationGroups"
Subjects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)/Subjects"

```

- Occurrences with pictures:

[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(58\)/Datastreams\(35\)/Observations?\\$expand=ObservationGroups\(\\$expand=Observations\),Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement,\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?$expand=ObservationGroups($expand=Observations),Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement,$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)))

```

▼ ObservationGroups:
  ▼ 0:
    @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservationGroups(11)"
    @iot.id: 11
    creationTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
    description: "Felis silvestris Occurrence 7"
    endTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
    name: "GatFerOcc7"
    Observations@iot.count: 3
  ▼ Observations:
    ▼ 0:
      @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393312)"
      @iot.id: 1393312
      phenomenonTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
      result: "https://www.qbif.org/species/7193910"
      resultTime: "2024-07-20T09:00:00Z"
    ▼ 1:
      @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393313)"
      @iot.id: 1393313
      phenomenonTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
      result: "https://www.infoambiental.arumets.cat/AD4GD_CameraTrap/04072024_0612_C3/04072024_0612_C3_01.JPG"
      resultTime: "2024-07-20T09:00:00Z"
    ▼ 2:
      @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Observations(1393314)"
      @iot.id: 1393314
      phenomenonTime: "2024-07-04T04:12:00Z"
      result: "https://www.infoambiental.arumets.cat/AD4GD_CameraTrap/04072024_0612_C3/04072024_0612_C3_02.JPG"
      resultTime: "2024-07-20T09:00:00Z"

```


2.3 PILOT 3 (AIR QUALITY)

As outlined in Deliverable D3.1 “Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration Model”, this pilot study explores the potential of IoT/low-cost sensor (LCS) data to enhance high-resolution air quality monitoring.

Two data networks were identified as the most relevant sources. The first is Sensor.Community, which provides freely accessible citizen science data from more than 11000 measurement locations across Europe, with most stations concentrated in Central Europe. The second is PurpleAir, whose data was available via OpenAQ until March 2024 but is no longer openly accessible. However, given PurpleAir’s relatively small contribution (around 500 stations across Europe), this change is not expected to significantly affect the pilot’s objectives or outcomes.

Both networks primarily monitor particulate matter concentrations (specifically PM10 and PM2.5) using nephelometric methods (based on light scattering). Data are made available in near-real time, accompanied by essential metadata such as location, timestamp, and sensor type. Figure 5 in Deliverable D3.1 illustrated strong spatial coverage in Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern Europe.

Despite their potential, several challenges remain when working with these novel air quality observations. These include large data volumes, sensor noise, measurement outliers, and the limited availability of dense, high-quality reference datasets. Additionally, APIs —such as the one provided by Sensor.Community —are not currently performant enough for true real-time data acquisition. As a result, data are processed in *reanalysis mode*, with the potential to evolve toward a near-real-time framework with a latency of approximately one to two days.

As in D3.1, statistical preprocessing, outlier filtering, and geostatistical interpolation methods such as Kriging are essential for deriving reliable spatial information from the sensor data. To further enhance data quality, we apply a machine learning (ML) correction based on the XGBoost framework. This model addresses known biases in IoT measurements, which arise from aerosol physics, sensor-specific limitations, and sensitivity to meteorological conditions. The model combines raw IoT PM measurements with meteorological variables—such as temperature, relative humidity, and boundary layer height—from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset (available via the Copernicus Climate Data Store; <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>). It is trained using high-quality reference measurements from the EEA air quality monitoring network (available via the EEA Air Quality Download Service; <https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/>).

The bias-corrected data are subsequently interpolated onto a regular 1 km latitude–longitude grid using penalized ordinary Kriging, restricted to regions in proximity to IoT stations. To further improve spatial coverage and fill gaps between sensors, we are developing an additional

dataset using a Universal Kriging framework. This approach optimally combines the corrected IoT data with the ensemble median from the CAMS regional air quality model (available via the Copernicus Atmosphere Data Store; <https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/>). To optimize processing and avoid redundancy with existing model outputs, the initial focus is on Central Europe, where IoT network density is highest.

The resulting datasets enable the creation of retrospective and near-real-time air quality maps. Figure 6 in Deliverable D3.1 showcased this approach using Sensor.Community data for the city of Sofia, generating air quality fields at unprecedented spatial resolution and revealing distinct pollution hotspots.

3 COMPONENTS

This chapter describes the different components used to handle the heterogeneous IoT data. It also presents the updates done in these components after the publication of the deliverable D3.1 “Heterogeneous IoT data integration model”.

3.1 MOBILISING DATA TO STAPLUS WITH EDC

AD4GD has adopted the last version of the Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) and PSNC has implemented some extensions to it. Using EDC, AD4GD has created a data space with two nodes that implements a federated catalog and the control plane. The first node is operated by PSNC and the other is operated by ATOS (both partners in the AD4GD project). The ATOS node is playing the role of data provider; on the other hand, PSNC is the consumer of the data. It means that the ATOS node is giving the access to the data to the PSNC node through the data space connector. The following figure illustrates this setup.

Figure 2: AD4GD GDDS architecture. The left-hand side illustrates the implementation of the data plane and the right-hand side the deployment of the control plane.

As the first step to demonstrate how to integrate citizen science data in the GDDS, more4nature has collaborated with AD4GD. In this collaboration, more4nature has given to AD4GD some data

to ingest in a Sensor Things API instance that is part of the data plane of their implementation of the GDDS. This data should become available through their EDC catalogue.

The access to the server side involves several calls to GET and POST request, some of them asynchronous:

1. Data or service discovery in a federated catalogue
2. Contract negotiation
3. Request transfer
4. Actual data download

Figure 3: Number of steps required to get a data transfer in the data space

In order to execute all these API calls, a client-side tool needs to be developed that is able to hide and encapsulate the complexities of these steps.

TAPIS is an API explorer and a table manager. TAPIS reads data and metadata from some supported APIs and some data file formats and structures the data as tables that can be managed and transformed. Internally, everything is a table that has columns that represent fields and rows that represent records. TAPIS is connected to the MiraMon Map Browser to represent spatial records. We have extended TAPIS to support the Data Space Protocol used by the EDC.

In order to demonstrate how the EDC works, we need to start by connecting to the EDC federated catalogue and get a list of assets that are accessible.

Figure 6: Data Space Protocol steps that start in contract negotiation and end in the actual file download

```

query
  contractnegotiations
  contractnegotiations
  74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c
  74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c
  74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c
  74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c
  74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c
  transferprocesses
  transferprocesses
  60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28
  60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28
  60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28
  60150cf9-a649-4446-8729-3e41875cbb28
  dataaddress
  public
  public
  
```

```

{
  "@id": "74b819e9-4867-4008-a204-aaa8af97e49c",
  "type": "CONSUMER",
  "protocol": "dataspace-protocol-http",
  "state": "FINALIZED",
  "counterPartyId": "provider",
  "counterPartyAddress": "https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/protocol",
  "callbackAddresses": [],
  "createdAt": 1747415720167,
  "contractAgreementId": "ee47d610-086d-44c4-a2c1-316f95ff6ddd",
  "@context": {
    "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
    "edc": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/",
    "odr1": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odr1/2/"
  }
}
  
```

Figure 7: Data Space Protocol steps as seen from the web browser debugger tool

In this case, the downloaded asset is not a file, but the response of the root element of a Sensor Things API resource that lists the types of entities available and the URL to get to them.

OGC query URL: <https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/public>

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

name	url
1 Observations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Observations
2 Datastreams	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Datastreams
3 FeaturesOfInterest	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/FeaturesOfInterest
4 HistoricalLocations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/HistoricalLocations
5 Locations	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Locations
6 ObservedProperties	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/ObservedProperties
7 Sensors	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Sensors
8 Things	https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnr.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/Things

Figure 8: List of all the types of entities available through the EDC

In TAPIS we can continue exploring the data by selecting one data stream representing the height of the water in a lake. We do a “sort by” to ensure chronologic order and we filter the values lower that -600 that are only nodata values. The relation between the assets in the EDC and the ISO catalog is realised through the assetId. The process to put in place a new contract is based on M2M (Machine to Machine) mechanisms, using REST API calls. After the conclusion of a new contract, the resources, so in this case the data stored by a FROST/STApplus server instance, can be accessed through the OGC SensorThings API. Of course, the access can be configured at the EDC level using for example a role-based access control (RBAC).

Figure 9: Selection of a particular data stream ,request of the observations that are ordered by time and filtered to remove nodata values

Figure 10: Water level changes in time, for a period of 3 months on a citizen science sensor in a lake

This section illustrates only a part of what is possible in TAPIS. During the project we have developed tools for adding data into STA and applying most of the expand, select, orderby and filter that is available in the standard. The following figure represents a list of all the tools specific for STA:

STA entities reading tool:

STA entities create, edit or delete tool:

Complex queries:

STA tools:

Figure 11: Tools representing functions behind the SensorThings API

The Help button is a good resource to learn more about these tools and the way they can be applied and combined to get exactly the information wanted. You can try TAPIS by going to the following URL: www.tapis.grumets.cat

3.2 MOBILISING SENSOR DATA WITH STA

The mobilisation of the data generated by the multiple and heterogeneous IoT sensors is realised through the tools provided by the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service. In the context of the AD4GD project, the three pilots are using different sources of IoT data in specific use cases. First of all, the pilot implemented in Berlin is retrieving water level, temperature and quality data. The biodiversity pilot located in Spain is using camera traps generated images of wild animals. Finally, the last pilot is exploiting a large number of different types of air quality sensors installed in all the Europe. This means to use at the end of the day a unique common standard and the related data model. In the first step of the AD4GD project, it was decided to use the OGC SensorThings API (STA) with an extension making the collected data FAIRer. As consequence, the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service converts all the incoming IoT data to the OGC SensorThings API Plus data model before the storage in the STAplus server located in Geneva and managed by the IoT Lab.

As already described in the deliverable D3.1, the architecture of the STApplus server encompasses a NGINX proxy. Different instances of the STApplus server are running and protected thanks to the NGINX proxy. This allows the team of developers to use different versions of the STApplus server which is in fact composed by a FROST server instance and two plugins, namely the STApplus plugin and the OAuth2 plugin. All instances of the STApplus server are running as Docker containers; this permits a fast deployment of a STApplus server, in particular if the configuration of a STApplus server is changed relatively frequently in the development phase of the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service.

Numerous modifications were done in the STApplus server deployment in the IoT Lab research infrastructure during the second part of the AD4GD project:

- The technical documentation of the STApplus/FROST server available online on GitLab at <https://gitlab.distantaccess.com/ad4gd/docker-frost-server> was updated in function of the progress of the development of the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service.
- The Docker Compose file, containing all the settings needed for the deployment of the STApplus/FROST server, was also updated with modified parameters taken into account the correction of bugs and errors linked to the FROST server. The dockerisation permits to quickly test and validate any little changes in the settings declared in the Docker Compose file.
- The scope used by the OAuth2 plugin was also modified from the value “openid” to the value “idp”. This change is the result of a better alignment with the technical documentation provided by Authenix. Indeed, all the settings employed by the OAuth2 plugin and Authenix are now available directly in the Docker Compose file.
- In relationship with the data protection, it is now possible to enforce the access to the data stored in the STApplus server to only authenticated users. Another option which was also implemented in the settings of the Docker Compose file is to allow an anonymous user to read the data published by the STApplus without the right to modify them. The fact that the authentication settings are directly placed in the Docker Compose file allows a tailor-made deployment in function of the level of security and data protection chosen by the data providers.
- The setting concerning the persistence in the FROST database was also modified, notably for the generation of automatic identifiers. This change permitted to solve a bug encountered during the tests realised with the STApplus/FROST server.
- More details related to the authentication with Authenix through the OAuth2 plugin were added in the technical documentation. This includes some concrete examples on how to do it, notably through the Postman tool. Different screenshots are available directly in the updated technical documentation.
- Some URLs were also modified in the FROST server configuration and in the NGINX proxy configuration to improve the user experience when using the OGC SensorThings API.

- Some typographical errors were also corrected across all the project available on GitLab.

The integration and the collection of new data generated by the three AD4GD pilots permitted to test, correct, improve and validate the modifications and updates done in the context of the STAplus server instances deployed by IoT Lab. The process of the STAplus server deployment through a Docker container was well improved during the second half of the AD4GD project.

The different versions and branches of the FROST/STAplus server are also available online on AD4GD GitHub at https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-STAplus_Server. Other components, services and tools are also published in the repositories on the GitHub dedicated to the AD4GD project at <https://github.com/AD4GD>. When any bugs were discovered in relationship with the FROST server, an issue for each bug was sent to the developers of the FROST server. Some suggestions to improve the usability or to add new potential features were also proposed to the developers of the FROST server. This allows to make the FROST server more aligned within the needs of the three pilots of the AD4GD project.

3.3 BERLIN LAKES UPLIFT AND AVAILABLE VIA STA

One of main goals of AD4GD was to design and implement the building blocks to support a Green Deal Data Space that will provide interoperability support for the heterogeneous and increasingly growing set of data and services available in the various action areas addressed by the GD. Accordingly, as described in D1.4, AD4GD has defined a modular semantic data model for green deal related data (known as the Green Deal Information Model – GDIM), including provenance metadata, which leverages and reuses related standards. On top of that, AD4GD is providing the mechanisms to enable different systems to exchange data with unambiguous meaning through the harmonization of data according to GDIM (also known as data uplift), and to enable an integrated data access for the execution of advanced data analytics to support the project's pilots.

The AD4GD approach for data harmonisation and integration is based on the adoption of Linked Data as a federated layer, combined with the use of knowledge graph technologies, where data is made available and combined according to the GDIM. This approach was used and demonstrated with various datasets from the project pilots (see D1.4).

For the pilot 1, data from lakes in Berlin (e.g., water level, water temperature) collected by the Wasserportal platform and meteorological data (e.g., air temperature, precipitation, evapotranspiration) from the Open Meteo platform is being harmonized according to GDIM through an automatic workflow, which is then used by the AI models to carry out analysis and predictions of lakes condition. Moreover, the harmonized data is made available via a SensorThings API enabling access through a standard interface, which in turn is made available via the EDC connector to be part of the AD4GD data space. In detail the automatic workflow carries out the following tasks (depicted in the figure below):

1. Data from different sources (Wasserportal, Open Meteo) are automatically collected into AD4GD Minio data storage
2. An MQTT broker has defined a topic that monitors and launches a python script when new data is published to the specified bucket
3. The script launches the data harmonization pipelines (DPI pipelines), sending as input the new dataset(s)
4. The data harmonization pipelines produce the harmonized data, and stores it in JSON-LD format back in Minio, in a different bucket
5. The AI models are launched, and the predictions are generated and stored back in Minio, in a different bucket
6. The prediction data can be visualized via the AD4GD UI
7. The harmonized data is also stored in a semantic triplestore in the pilot data graph
8. The AD4GD STA generation service automatically generates a SensorThings API from the pilot data graph. Since this is a live endpoint, new data is automatically accessible from the endpoint.
9. The STA endpoint is also registered as an asset in AD4GD EDC connector. So other participants in the data space can access this endpoint at any time after the contract negotiation

Having the data harmonized provides multiple benefits:

- Integration of data from different sources
- Standardized data representation, i.e., based on the GDIM which leverages the OGC/W3C standard SOSA ontology for the representation of the observations/measurements
- Linking with reference and/or standard observable properties. AD4GD defined various observable properties, accessible via the OGC Rainbow service <https://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/vocab/>, which are aligned, when possible, with other standard vocabularies. For example, measurements about water temperature refer to the observable property: <https://w3id.org/ad4gd/water-quality/properties/water-temperature>, which is aligned with agrovov, saref and other ontologies/vocabularies.
- Linking with standard units of measurements. In particular, as prescribed in GDIM, we use QUDT units of measurements. For example, for the measurements about water temperature refer to the Celsius degrees unit: http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/DEG_C

Figures 13 and 14 show a sample input water level from one lake in a particular day that is provided as CSV, and the output of harmonized data in JSON-LD.

The water level STA endpoint automatically generated is available at:

- <https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw1.paas.psnc.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/>

- <https://sensor-things-api-sensor-things-api.apps.dcw.lpaas.psnc.pl/WasserPortalDaily/api/v1.0/docs> (Swagger)

Figure 12: Automatic semantic uplift workflow for pilot1 data

5800310_wasserstand_tw_13_04_2025					
Datum	Tagesmittelwert	Stationsnummer: 5800310	Stationsname: Waldsee Zehlendorf	Gewässer: Waldsee Zehlendorf	Wasserstand in cm
13.04.2025	52				
14.04.2025	51				
15.04.2025	50				
16.04.2025	49				
17.04.2025	48				
18.04.2025	47				
19.04.2025	49				
20.04.2025	48				
21.04.2025	-777				

Figure 13: Sample input dataset about water level in one lake in Berlin


```

>
"@context": { ...
},
"@id": "http://w3id.org/ad4gd/pilot1/lake/waterlevel/observationCollection/5800310-5831922113",
"@type": "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/ObservationCollection",
"identifier": "waterlevel-5800310-5831922113",
"label": "Water level observation collection for lake Waldsee Zehlendorf sensor 5800310 ",
"hasFeatureOfInterest": [
  {
    "@id": "http://w3id.org/ad4gd/berlin/lake/5831922113",
    "@type": [
      "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/FeatureOfInterest",
      "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Lake"
    ],
    "identifier": {
      "@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer",
      "@value": 5831922113
    },
    "http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry": {
      "@id": "http://w3id.org/ad4gd/berlin/lake/5831922113/geo",
      "@type": [
        "http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#Geometry",
        "http://www.opengis.net/ont/sf#MultiPolygon"
      ],
      "http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT": {
        "@type": "http://www.openlinksw.com/schemas/virtrdf#Geometry",
        "@value": "MULTIPOLYGON(((13.23455 52.44122,13.23472 52.4411,13.23466 52.44108,13.2346 52.44105,
      },
      "label": {
        "@language": "en",
        "@value": "Geometry for lake Waldsee Zehlendorf"
      }
    },
    "label": {
      "@language": "en",
      "@value": "Lake Waldsee Zehlendorf"
    }
  },
  {
    "hasMember": [

```

Figure 14: Sample output harmonized dataset about water level in one lake in Berlin

4 SIMPL INITIATIVE MONITORING

The AD4GD project continues to monitor the progress done in relationship with the SIMPL middleware. As already described in the related chapter in the deliverable D3.1, SIMPL is a smart middleware in development supported by the European Union. This middleware should ease the federation of cloud and edge computing in the context of the different European projects concerning the data spaces. The AD4GD project is following the development of SIMPL because it can be a good solution to solve the challenges mentioned in the Task T3.3, in particular the edge computing optimisation and the scalability when exchanging data between the edge and the cloud. In the context of AD4GD, the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) is composed by four layers addressed also by the SIMPL middleware: Internet of Things (IoT), edge, cloud and finally, High-Performance Computing (HPC). The different sorts of sensors used in the three pilots are of course placed at the IoT layer and some data processing activities are done at the edge, for example to reduce the traffic to the cloud. A component of the AD4GD cloud is the instantiation of the STAplus/FROST server which stores the IoT data generated by the heterogeneous sensors. On the HPC, the data processing through the AI/ML modules or services is executed to determine for example the trend and the prediction of the different measurements.

Several initial risks were already identified in the first phase of the AD4GD project: the tight schedule between the release of the SIMPL middleware and the end of the AD4GD project programmed in August 2025, the maturity of the SIMPL middleware in its initial release and possible remaining bugs. The SIMPL-Open Development Roadmap for 2025 and 2026 has been published the 14th February 2025 and is available publicly online at the URL <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/group/simpl-forum/discussion/simpl-open-development-roadmap-2025-2026>. The picture below is directly taken from the mentioned URL:

Simpl-Open roadmap 2025-26

Figure 15: SIMPL roadmap for 2025 and 2026

The observations done by examining the SIMPL roadmap confirm the risks elaborated and explained in the context of the previous deliverable D3.1. Indeed, most of the activities undertaken in 2025 for the development of the SIMPL middleware will not be finished or will be not sufficiently advanced before the end of the AD4GD project. In consequence, it is very unlikely that the AD4GD project will be an early adopter of the SIMPL solution. Of course, the utilisation of the SIMPL middleware can be studied and applied in a new project following the AD4GD project, in function of the future outcomes of the SIMPL development.

5 EDGE COMPUTING

The definition of edge computing consists of a distributed computing topology with data processing executed near their production. For instance, in the AD4GD case, the processing of the images generated by the camera traps installed for the pilot on biodiversity can avoid sending empty pictures to the cloud or pictures showing a human. Another use case implemented in the project is the utilisation of filters, typically a Kalman filter, to reduce the sending of the same data or information. The Kalman filter² is largely used in the context of signal processing which includes scientific measurements such as the temperature or the sound level. The Kalman filter is particularly adequate for data represented in time series, which is exactly the case in the AD4GD project. Indeed, the storage on the STAplus/FROST server is realised through the principles of time series and geolocation. Another kind of filtering applied in the pilots is automatic removal of false data. For example, the sensors used to monitor the water level and quality installed in the small lakes in the city of Berlin are not always active and when no data are received from them, a value “-777” is placed in the CSV files generated and published by the Berlin Wasserportal. To avoid storing such defective values on the STAplus/FROST server, a filtering process is executed before the conversion of the data to the format defined by the OGC SensorThings API and these wrong values are discarded.

5.1 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

This section of the deliverable D3.2 presents different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the availability of the data registered into the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) designed by the AD4GD project. The goal is also to improve the accessibility and the usage of the data for the different stakeholders engaged in the project, typically the researchers and the citizens involved in the three pilots. At the same time, these KPIs are used to measure the scalability and the optimisation realised at the edge of the Green Deal Data Space.

A list of useful Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was compiled below :

- Number of available datasets: This KPI permits to evaluate the number of datasets which are available in the AD4GD Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). All these datasets were generated by components installed at the edge, such as IoT sensors, other devices placed at the edge and storage deployed at the edge. Two components are in charge of the storage at the cloud level, namely the STAplus/FROST server and the MinIO server, which is acting as a file storage for the AD4GD project.

² Kalman filter: <https://www.kalmanfilter.net/default.aspx>

- **Discarded value count:** This KPI takes into account the number of data which were discarded for different reasons at the edge. For instance, the data which are false like the value -777 encountered at the level of the Berlin Wasserportal are ignored. This KPI also encompasses the data dropped by the filtering applied at the edge, such the Kalman filter. The idea behind the discarded value count KPI is to reduce the sending of irrelevant data to the cloud; this is reducing a part of the required network bandwidth.
- **Number of requests handled per minute:** The KPI is used to evaluate the number of needed requests to be sent to the STAplus/FROST server. As the discarded value count, this KPI is evaluating the reduction of exchanges between the edge and the cloud, and also, the optimisation and the scalability to be applied at the edge computing. As the STAplus/FROST server is the main component of the GDDS to store the heterogeneous IoT data, this KPI is important to ensure a smooth operation and a good scalability of this server.
- **Latency related to the retrieval of data stored by the GDDS:** A supplementary KPI related to the latency measured when the data of the GDDS are retrieved from the STAplus/FROST server. This KPI plays an important role when the IoT data registered in the STAplus/FROST server are read and shown on a map or a chart; in these two cases, a large amount of data can be requested by the final users of a map or a chart.

5.2 ACTIONS

This section explains the different actions taken to improve the scalability at the edge level and also the performance at the same time. The idea behind is to optimise the data flow generated by the heterogeneous sensors at the edge and to reduce the amount of data to be transferred to the cloud which is storing the data into different locations and servers, typically on MinIO and on STAplus/FROST server.

The actions are based on the KPIs defined in the previous section of this deliverable. First, the first action undertaken in relation with the Task T3.3 is to reduce the number of incorrect data; this is of course directly related to the KPI on discarded value count. As already mentioned previously, CSV files generated and published by the Berlin Wasserportal contain values of -777 when the data are not available at the time of the requests to the Wasserportal API. Naturally, a filter was put in place to ignore systematically the values of -777.

The second action also directly associated to the discarded value count is to apply a Kalman filter at the edge inside the IoT sensors using directly the SensorThings API. These IoT sensors were programmed and installed in Geneva in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. A Kalman filter is basically an algorithm used to determine the values of a giving system, in our case an IoT sensor, taking into account that the measurements observed over time can be noisy. The results after the application of a Kalman filter are better, as the different accuracies are handled by this algorithm. In consequence, the errors of measurements in real time are reduced. The objective was also to limit the number of IoT data to be sent to the cloud, more precisely to the

STApplus/FROST server, when the values of measurements don't change significantly over time. Indeed, it is somehow useless to send regularly very similar IoT data at a rather high frequency. It is better indeed to send the IoT data only when a significant variation is spotted by the IoT sensors. It means that the required network bandwidth is reduced, which is an important element to take into account for a large deployment of IoT sensors. Using a threshold in the Kalman filter permits to reach the defined objective. The results obtained are shown in the following figure:

Figure 16: Kalman filter for IoT sensors

The points in green on the above figure are the data effectively sent to the STApplus/FROST server and the points in red are the ignored values. When the variation is not reaching the defined threshold, in this case a threshold of 0.5, the values are not sent. The discarded value count corresponds to 121 values or 47.3% of the total measurements. Applying the Kalman filter to all the heterogeneous IoT sensors can potentially reduce almost of 50% of the amount of data to be transmitted to the cloud, which is of course not negligible.

The number of requests handled per minute is also an KPI where improvements were executed. The context is the air quality data collected through the online Sensor.Community platform located at <https://sensor.community/en/>. Everybody can buy an air quality sensor and install at home for instance. Then, the data concerning the air quality, such as the values of PM2.5, are

sent to the Sensor.Community platform and displayed on an online map as illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 17: Sensor.Community map

It is also possible to retrieve the old data received previously on the Sensor.Community at <https://archive.sensor.community/>. Here the data are classified by date under the format of CSV files. These files are particularly voluminous with several GBs when the files are compressed. After uncompressing, the data for only one month of measurements take between 4 and 12 GBs of space, depending on the sort of air quality sensors. It was decided as first approach to use the following models of IoT air quality sensors: BME280, DHT22 and SDS011. Each line of a CSV should be converted to an Observation as specified by the OGC SensorThings API data model. It means that for the month of August 2024, the following numbers of observations should be sent and stored by the FROST/STApplus server:

- BME280 IoT sensors: 82'770'073 observations
- DHT22 IoT sensors: 70'657'908 observations
- SDS011 IoT sensors: 185'690'033 observations

The total number of observations for August 2024 corresponds to 339'118'014. Initially, it was planned to read each CSV file line by line, to handle the data conversion for one line and then, to send the data to the FROST/STApplus server using the OGC SensorThings API. This approach is designed to reduce the required resources such the RAM and avoids loading a whole CSV file at the beginning of the data processing. In more details, the complete data processing is composed by:

1. Read the current line from the CSV file.
2. Retrieve the following data from the line:
 - a. Sensor identifier
 - b. Sensor type
 - c. Latitude
 - d. Longitude
 - e. Timestamp
3. In function of the type of IoT sensors:
 - a. Retrieve the values of PM10 and PM2.5 (SDS011).
 - b. Retrieve the values of air pressure, temperature and humidity (BME280).
 - c. Retrieve the values for the air temperature and humidity (DHT22).
4. Check if the entity, in fact a Thing representing the IoT sensor, is already existing on the FROST/STApplus server.
5. If not, create it.
6. Get the URL of the Thing corresponding to the IoT sensor.
7. Prepare the payload to be sent to the FROST/STApplus server.
8. Based on the URL retrieved in the point 6, get the endpoint (URL) of the observations for this Thing.
9. Finally, send the data to the FROST/STApplus server.

The time needed to register all the observation was calculated through different tests. The main results are showing that almost three weeks are required to save all the data to the FROST/STApplus server and that the number of requests handled by minutes is pretty high. Indeed, a lot of requests are needed only to determine if the entity for a given IoT sensor is already existing and to retrieve the complete URLs where to send afterwards the payload containing the data initially read from a CSV file. It is in fact rather inefficient due to the large number of necessary requests.

To improve the situation by reducing the number of requests needed to send all the observations to the FROST/STApplus, the batch requests feature available on the OGC SensorThings API was used. It allows in our case to send 500 observations for a request. A batch request contains a particular HTTP header named "Content-Type" with a value of "multipart/mixed". The main advantage of a batch request is the possibility in the same request to create a new Thing entity if it doesn't yet exist, and to send the observations associated to this entity at the same time. This reduces of course the number of requests handled by minutes: indeed, less requests are needed as most of the data and other information, like the metadata, can be sent in only one request. More details related to the batch requests can be found in the OGC SensorThings API at <https://docs.ogc.org/is/18-088/18-088.html#batch-requests>. The examples related to the batch requests features are not so detailed in fact when implementing and using this feature in the context of the sending of air quality data. Some tests were successfully conducted in the AD4GD development environment to demonstrate the reduction

of the time required to save all the observations from the CSV files to the FROST/STApplus server.

The last action undertaken concerns the latency. The context is how to retrieve all the IoT sensor data stored in the FROST/STApplus server to display them on a map or on a chart for the visualisation. Different tests were done to determine the better way to reduce the latency.

Originally, it was decided to display all the information contained in the FROST/STApplus server on map with a chart generated automatically for each type of data. This initial work was done with PHP using the Symfony framework. The obtained map is then using a frontend and a backend written in PHP. The loading of the data stored on the FROST/STApplus server can take several seconds to be completed. The OGC SensorThings API is employed to retrieve the data from the FROST/STApplus server using the backend written in PHP. The latency was very high in this case and the users should wait a long time. So, some improvements were required to reduce the latency.

A Java middleware was developed to support the OGC SensorThings API and to realise the communication between the map and the FROST/STApplus server. The Java middleware is acting as a translator between the OGC SensorThings API. Adding a new component between the PHP code and the FROST/STApplus server could be counterintuitive, but immediate good results were collected. Indeed, in the latest version, the PHP frontend forwards the request from the user to the backend implemented through the Symfony framework: a specific route is available for this purpose. Then, the request realised by the user is transmitted to the Java middleware which converts the request to a call to the corresponding OGC SensorThings API endpoint located directly on the FROST/STApplus server installed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure in Geneva. Globally, the latency measured when reading the data stored on the FROST/STApplus server is significantly reduced: indeed, a factor between 4 and 5 was measured during the tests when loading the data, compared to the original implementation. It means that the user doesn't need to wait for the data for several seconds. The main difference between Java and PHP explaining the better results obtained by the Java code is essentially the support of concurrency. Indeed, PHP has in fact a limited support concerning the concurrency; on the other hand, Java is well recognised for its robust support for multithreading and concurrency. Furthermore, a cache was put in place at the Symfony side: it again reduces the latency with a factor comprised from 2 to 3. This experiment shows that a frontend and a backend purely written in PHP cannot be used to directly retrieve all the data contained in a FROST/STApplus server, despite the fact that this backend implements the OGC SensorThings API. It is far advantageous in this case to implement the OGC SensorThings API in a dedicated middleware written in Java. This middleware acts as a bridge between the frontend and the backend on one side, and the FROST/STApplus server on the other side.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The deliverable D3.2 “Scalability and edge computing optimization” has reported the progress done in the second half of the AD4GD project for the Internet of Things (IoT) part. Furthermore, the edge computing, which is playing an important role in the context of IoT, was presented and discussed: several KPIs were elaborated to better measure the performance and the scalability at the edge of the future Green Deal Data Space. Some actions were proposed and applied to improve the scalability and other points related to the specific KPIs.

The IoT multi-protocol parser as a service can be extended to receive more data from the pilots depending on eventual new communication protocols used by possible future IoT sensors and devices installed in the different regions linked to the AD4GD pilots. The interoperability and the harmonisation of the heterogeneous IoT data were improved during the second half of the project, thanks to the updated versions of the different IoT components developed in the context of the Green Deal Data Space.

Finally, the AD4GD project expects that the SIMPL middleware will be available soon. It will be then possible to install and test it with the real IoT data collected during the AD4GD project. As the time constraint concerning the end of the project is important, it was not doable to deploy and test the current development of the SIMPL middleware with the GDDS building blocks and data during the AD4GD project. We recommend to install the SIMPL middleware in the project succeeding to the AD4GD project.

7 REFERENCES

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